

Empirical modeling of the distribution of prime numbers and fixed-initial-digit twins

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1 Introduction

The distribution of prime numbers is one of the most fascinating mysteries in number theory. Although their average density has been studied extensively using tools such as the prime counting function or the prime number theorem, their local distribution remains unpredictable. In this article, we propose an empirical and algorithmic approach to predict the position of the next prime number from a given prime number, by studying a function of the form $p_2 = 2p_1 - z$. This exploration, although not rigorously demonstrated, highlights certain numerical regularities, particularly in the particular case of twin primes. We will also develop a family of formulas inspired by Willans' formula to locate these twins based on their initial digit. This attempt is part of an experimental approach aimed at approaching a possible structure hidden behind the apparent irregularity of prime numbers.

2 Starting Function

The starting point of this study is an equation that can be reformulated as a function: $2p_1 - z = p_2$ where p_1 denotes a given prime number, p_2 the next prime number, and z the positive integer that is subtracted from twice p_1 to obtain p_2 . We assume that z is always a strictly positive integer. To examine the properties of this function, we applied it to prime numbers between 1 and 200. To avoid unnecessarily burdensome material, only some representative excerpts of the results will be presented in the remainder of this article.

2.1 Results

We observe that the variation in the value of z from one calculation to the next never takes the value 1. This absence is explained by the constraint imposed on z : it must necessarily be an odd number. However, if we add 1 to an odd number, it becomes even—which violates our initial hypothesis. This property

p_1	p_2	$z = 2p_1 - p_2$	$x = \frac{z}{p_1}$
2	3	1	0.50
3	5	1	0.33
5	7	3	0.60
23	29	17	0.74
29	31	27	0.93
127	131	123	0.97
131	137	125	0.95
197	199	195	0.99

Table 1: Values of the function $f(p_1) = 2p_1 - z = p_2$

can be demonstrated simply:

$$2p_1 - z = p_2 \tag{1}$$

$$2(p_1 - z) = p_2 \tag{2}$$

$$2 \times pz = p_2 \quad \text{with } pz = p_1 - z \tag{3}$$

$$\tag{4}$$

If z were even, this would mean that we could obtain the value of the next prime number by multiplying an integer by 2, which is contrary to the definition of a prime number.

3 First Resolution Interval

Using the formula: $2p_1 - z = p_2$, we can establish a first interval that encloses the value of p_2 : We know that z is a positive integer that is subtracted from twice p_1 to obtain p_2 . Thus, $2p_1$ must be greater than p_2 and p_2 greater than p_1 :

$$\boxed{p_2 \subset]p_1; 2p_1[} \tag{5}$$

However, we do not take z into account within this interval, which prevents us from getting closer to the true value of p_2 .

4 Study of z

- We can prove that z is related to the gap between p_2 and p_1 :

$$2p_1 - z = p_2 \quad (6)$$

$$z = 2p_1 - p_2 \quad (7)$$

$$p_1 - z = p_1 - (2p_1 - p_2) \quad (8)$$

$$p_1 - z = p_1 - 2p_1 + p_2 \quad (9)$$

$$p_1 - z = p_2 - p_1 \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Thus,} \quad (11)$$

$$2p_1 - z = p_1 - (p_2 - p_1) \quad (12)$$

$$(13)$$

- We can also show that $p_1 > z$ by relying on the fact that $z > 0$, by proving it by contradiction:

$$2p_1 - z = p_2 \quad (14)$$

$$p_1 + p_1 - z = p_2 \quad (15)$$

$$p_1 - y = p_2 \quad \text{with } y = p_1 - z \quad (16)$$

$$(17)$$

If $p_1 > z$ we would then have $p_2 < p_1$ which does not seem consistent. We will now study the resemblance between the value of p_1 and z .

4.1 Relationship between p_1 and z

Let us call "x" the value obtained by $\frac{z}{p_1}$. We will now study the growth of x as a function of the value of p_1 :

p_1	z	$x = \frac{z}{p_1}$	Numerical value of x
2	1	$\frac{1}{2}$	0.50
3	1	$\frac{1}{3}$	0.333...
5	4	$\frac{4}{5}$	0.80
23	17	$\frac{17}{23}$	0.739
29	27	$\frac{27}{29}$	0.931
127	123	$\frac{123}{127}$	0.968
131	125	$\frac{125}{131}$	0.954
197	195	$\frac{195}{197}$	0.990

Table 2: Evolution of $x = \frac{z}{p_1}$ according to the value of p_1

According to these results, x is very unstable. Indeed, from one prime number to another, its value can decrease drastically.

Nevertheless, it seems to get closer and closer to 1 the higher p_1 is:

$$\boxed{\lim_{p_1 \rightarrow \infty} x = 1} \quad (18)$$

(19)

We can prove this limit:

We want to prove: (20)

$$\lim_{p_1 \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{2p_1 - p_2}{p_1} \right) = 1 \quad (21)$$

In our function let $p_2 = g + p_1$ with g the average gap: (22)

$$\frac{2p_1 - p_2}{p_1} \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{2p_1 - (p_1 + g)}{p_1} \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{p_1 + g}{p_1} \quad (25)$$

$$1 - \frac{g}{p_1} \quad (26)$$

According to PNT: $\boxed{g \approx \log(p_1)}$ (27)

Then: (28)

$$1 - \frac{g}{p_1} \approx 1 - \frac{\log(p_1)}{p_1} \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{\log(p_1)}{p_1} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } p_1 \rightarrow \infty \quad (30)$$

Therefore: (31)

$$\lim_{p_1 \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{2p_1 - p_2}{p_1} \right) = 1 \quad (32)$$

We can thus draw a graph illustrating this limit:

4.2 Relationship between x and twin primes

When we look more closely at the increase in x , we notice that whenever p_1 is a twin prime number that begins with a 2, x begins with a decimal series of 9s:

p_1	p_2	$\frac{2p_1-p_2}{p_1}$	Approx. Value
27	29	$\frac{2 \times 27 - 29}{27}$	0.9259
227	229	$\frac{2 \times 227 - 229}{227}$	0.9907
2027	2029	$\frac{2 \times 2027 - 2029}{2027}$	0.9990
20027	20029	$\frac{2 \times 20027 - 20029}{20027}$	0.9999

Table 3: Growth of decimal 9s in $x = \frac{2p_1-p_2}{p_1}$ for twin primes starting with 2

For a value of p_1 less than the next value of x , x will never be greater than 0.9. We can thus imagine a mathematical formula that would give us the value of the next twin prime number beginning with a 2:

$$g(n, i) = (10^{-i+1} - 10^{-i}) - \frac{\left(2 \times \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{2^n} \left[\left(\frac{n}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^k \lfloor \cos^2(\pi \cdot \frac{(j+1)}{j+1+j}) \rfloor} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right] \right] - \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{2^{n+1}} \left[\left(\frac{n+1}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^k \lfloor \cos^2(\pi \cdot \frac{(j+1)}{j+1+j}) \rfloor} \right)^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \right] \right] \right)}{\left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{2^n} \left[\left(\frac{n}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^k \lfloor \cos^2(\pi \cdot \frac{(j+1)}{j+1+j}) \rfloor} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right] \right]}$$

(33)

(34)

$$g(n, i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{si } g(i, n) > 0 \\ 1 & \text{si } g(i, n) < 0 \\ n + 1 & \text{si } g(i, n) = 0 \\ i + 1 \text{ and } n + 1 & \text{si } g(i, n) = 1 \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

This formula, which is based on Willans' formula, allows us to calculate the position of the next twin prime number starting with a 2. If the result is equal to 1 for the first time with respect to a given value of i , then the prime number obtained by the value of n is a twin prime number starting with a 2. After obtaining 1, we add i to 1, as well as to n to calculate the next twin prime number starting with a 2. Conversely, If the function gives us 0, we must add n to 1 to calculate the result of the function obtained by the next prime number.

4.3 Explanation of the different terms

- $(10^{-i+1} - 10^{-i})$ is a minimum value that allows us to determine whether the second part of the formula is greater than or less than the decimal sequence of 9. For $i = 1$, to determine the position of the first twin number beginning with a two, we have $(10^{-1+1} - 10^{-1}) = (1 - 0.1) = 0.9$, so we will have a negative result if the second part of the formula is greater than 0.9. Since this result is negative, it will be converted to 1.

1.

- $2 \times \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{2^n} \left[\left(\frac{n}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^k \lfloor \cos^2(\pi \cdot \frac{(j+1)}{j+1+j}) \rfloor} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right] \right]$ corresponds, according to Cillans' formula, to the next prime number, which in our case is p_1 , because p_2 will correspond to the prime number after p_1 . This term is simply $2p_1$

- $\left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{2^{n+1}} \left[\left(\frac{n+1}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^k \left[\cos^2 \left(\pi \cdot \frac{(j+1)}{j^1+j} \right) \right] \right)^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \right] \right]$ corresponds to the prime number after p_1 , which explains the use of " $n + 1$ ". This term is similar to p_2 .
- the fraction corresponds to $\frac{2p_1 - p_2}{p_1}$, which is therefore equal to x .

4.4 Simplified Formula

We can also write a much more simplified formula that gives exactly the same results as the formula based on Willans' formula:

$$g(i) = (10^{1-i} - 10^{-i}) - \frac{2 \times p_1 - p_2}{p_1} \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } g(i) > 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } g(i) < 0 \\ \text{shift by a prime number} & \text{if } g(i) = 0 \\ i + 1 \text{ and shift by a prime number} & \text{if } g(i) = 1 \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

This graph illustrates the results of an automated analysis of the formula's accuracy with respect to twin primes up to 10^{10} significant numbers. This

analysis was produced by a Python script using our formula and verifying each time that for $g(i)=1$ for the first time as a function of the value of i , we obtain a twin prime starting with a 2. Our formula thus only yields twin primes starting with a 2.

4.5 Formula Limit

Although 100% accurate, our formula only yields the first twin primes starting with a 2, and it only yields one twin prime for each length (in number of digits): (29(2 digits)),227(3 digits),2027(4 digits),...

5 Formula for predicting p_2 as a function of p_1

Despite the irregularity of the distribution of prime numbers, based on our results and observations, we can establish a general function to approximate the next prime number as a function of the known prime number (p_1):

$$\boxed{p(i, p_1) = 2 \times p_1 - p_1 \times (10^{1-i} - 10^{-i})} \quad (37)$$

The variable i depends directly on the formula that gives us the twin prime numbers starting with a 2 and which are prime with respect to their significant digits. We take the position of the twin prime number starting with a 2 and then apply this value to i . Example: We know the prime number 53 but we do not know the next prime number. According to our formula, the last twin prime number starting with a 2 and prime with respect to its significant digit is 29. 29 is the very first twin prime number starting with a 2 that has two digits. So i will be equal to 1:

$$p(1, 53) = 2 \times 53 - 53 \times (10^{1-1} - 10^{-1}) \quad (38)$$

$$= 106 - 53 \times (0.9) \quad (39)$$

$$= 106 - 47.7 \quad (40)$$

$$= 58.3 \quad (41)$$

$$(42)$$

The next prime number after 53 is 59. So for $p(1,53)$ our formula was 98.81 % accurate. However, this formula is more useful to approximate the position of the next prime by using an interval:

$$p_2 \in]2p_1 - p_1((10^{-i} - 10^{-i+1})); 2p_1 - p_1((10^{1-i} - 10^{-i})[\quad (43)$$

$$\boxed{p_2 \in]p(i + 1, p_1); p(i, p_1)[} \quad (44)$$

$$(45)$$

6 An Infinite Number of Formulas for an Infinite Number of Twin Numbers

We conjecture that there are infinitely many formulas that allow us to obtain the position of an infinite number of twin prime numbers starting with 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, etc., and that are prime with respect to their length (number of digits). Behind this infinite number of formulas lies a function that is the key to obtaining them:

$$g(n, i, c) = ((c - 2) + (10^{-i+1} - 10^{-i})) - \frac{\left(c \times \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{2^n} \left[\left(\frac{n}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^k \lfloor \cos^2(\pi \cdot \frac{(j+1)}{j+1+j}) \rfloor} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right] \right] - \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{2^{n+1}} \left[\left(\frac{n+1}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^k \lfloor \cos^2(\pi \cdot \frac{(j+1)}{j+1+j}) \rfloor} \right)^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \right] \right] \right)}{\left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{2^n} \left[\left(\frac{n}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^k \lfloor \cos^2(\pi \cdot \frac{(j+1)}{j+1+j}) \rfloor} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right] \right]} \quad (46)$$

$$g(n, i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } g(i, n, c) > 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } g(i, n, c) < 0 \\ n + 1 & \text{if } g(i, n, c) = 0 \\ i + 1 \text{ et } n + 1 & \text{if } g(i, n, c) = 1 \end{cases} \quad (47)$$

"c" is the digit our twin prime number begins with, so to find twin prime numbers beginning with a 2 like 29, c will be equal to 2.

6.1 Limit

This function will not be able to find twin prime numbers with a length (number of digits) equal to 1. The second part of this function relies on Willians' formula, which is very complex to use. This function does not work for twin prime numbers beginning with 1.

6.2 Function Proof

We want to find the position of the first twin prime number beginning with a 3 that has 3 digits:

$$c = 3 \quad (48)$$

$$i = 1 \quad (49)$$

$$((c - 2) + (10^{-i+1} - 10^{-i})) = (1 + 0, 9) = 1,9 \quad (50)$$

The function returns 0 for all prime numbers less than 311, but when we get to 311, we observe this:

$$1.9 - \frac{3 \times 311 - 313}{311} \approx -0.09 \quad (51)$$

The function gives us a negative result for 311, which is output as 1. The function has therefore successfully detected the first twin number starting with a 3 with 3 digits.

7 Simplified Formulation

We can write the formula as:

$$g(i, c, p_1, p_2) = ((c - 2) + (10^{1-i} - 10^{-i})) - \frac{c \times p_1 - p_2}{p_1} \quad (52)$$

8 Potential Proof of an Infinitely Many Twin Primes

It has already been proven that the gap between prime numbers keeps increasing. For a fixed value of i and c , there will be a point where the result of the function drops into the negative. Proving that my function works for all twin primes would prove that there are an infinitely many of them.

Conclusion

Our study proposes an attempt to empirically model the distribution of prime numbers and, more specifically, twin primes using a simple model based on the function $p_2 = 2p_1 - z$. Despite obvious limitations, notably the approximation and the dependence of certain formulas on prior knowledge of p_2 , the numerical results reveal interesting regularities, notably the appearance of values of $x = \frac{z}{p_1}$ close to 1. The use of a variant of Willans' formula successfully detected particular twin numbers, paving the way for the formulation of generalized functions. Finally, we outlined a conjecture according to which there exist an infinite number of such formulas, which could provide a novel approach to exploring the hypothesis of infinite twin primes. Future work could aim to refine these formulas and attempt a rigorous formalization of these empirical observations.